

Original Research

Comparing XGBoost and ARCH-LM Models for IPO Valuation in the Iranian Capital Market

Fatemeh Malmir¹

Department of accounting, Bo.C., Islamic Azad University, Borujerd, Iran

Farshid Kheirollahi¹

Department of Accounting, Faculty Economic and Accounting, Razi University, Kermanshah, Iran

Hossein Yarahmadi¹

Department of Computer Engineering, Bo.C., Islamic Azad University, Borujerd, Iran, Iran

Farid Sefaty¹

Department of Accounting, Bo.C., Islamic Azad University, Borujerd, Iran

Received 21 August 2025 Revised 1 October 2025 Accepted 4 October 2025

Abstract

The main objective of this research is to conduct a rigorous comparative analysis of the performance of the eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm against the traditional Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (ARCH-LM) model in predicting initial public offering (IPO) valuation ratios in the Iranian capital market. This study focuses on three key dependent valuation variables: the market-to-book value ratio (m2b), the enterprise value-to-assets ratio (v2a), and the enterprise value-to-sales ratio (v2s). Utilizing a cross-sectional dataset of 163 Iranian companies (42 listed and 121 over-the-counter) during the 2013-2023 fiscal period, the research employs a robust out-of-sample validation approach. Performance is benchmarked using prediction accuracy, economic significance, and computational efficiency. Diebold-Mariano tests and bootstrapping were applied to ensure the statistical significance of predictive differences between the models. The comparative analysis revealed that the XGBoost model demonstrates statistically significant superiority over the ARCH-LM model across all predictive metrics. The out-of-sample (OOS) Coefficient of Determination (R²) showed an improvement ranging from 9.7% to 10.9% across the valuation ratios, with a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) reduction between 32.6% and 35.5%. The OOS R² values for XGBoost ranged from 0.715 to 0.768, with all predictive differences confirmed as significant ($p < 0.01$). XGBoost offers a substantially more accurate and robust framework for IPO valuation compared to ARCH-LM, providing

¹ Corresponding author's Email: f.kheirollahi@razi.ac.ir

considerable economic advantages. While the machine learning approach entails higher computational demands, its superior predictive accuracy suggests its potential as a more effective tool for risk mitigation and decision-making, supporting the modernization of valuation practices in the Iranian market. Way for the digitalization of valuation processes in the Iranian market.

Keywords: ARCH-LM, Initial Public Offerings (IPOs), Iranian Stock Market, Valuation Ratios, XGBoost.

Introduction

An Initial Public Offering (IPO) is one of the most significant financial events in a company's life cycle, during which private and state-owned enterprises offer their shares to the public capital market for the first time (Borisov et al, 2021). This process not only provides companies with access to broader financial resources but also creates new investment opportunities for the general public (Shuwaikh & Dubocage, 2022). However, inaccuracies in IPO pricing can have severe and irreversible consequences (Chen et al, 2018). Overpricing can lead to a lack of investor interest and failure to raise the required capital, while underpricing results in a substantial loss of potential funds for the company. Global statistics indicate that approximately 23% of IPOs underperform in their first year, a figure that can reach as high as 40% in some markets, highlighting the critical importance of precision in evaluating this type of investment (Krug & Herberger, 2022; Filipovic & Seistrjakov, 2024). The Tehran Stock Exchange (TSE) and Iran Fara Bourse face similar challenges, with distinctive characteristics that make them particularly relevant for analysis. A comprehensive examination of IPO performance in the Iranian capital market from 2013 to 2023 reveals that nearly 35% of these offerings have underperformed within the first six months of trading. This specific timeframe (2013-2023) was selected as it encompasses both bull and bear market cycles in Iran, providing a robust dataset across varying economic conditions and regulatory frameworks. This phenomenon has affected investor confidence, limited available financial resources for companies, and reduced overall capital market efficiency. Given the significant role of capital markets in Iran's economic development and the ongoing privatization efforts, enhancing IPO evaluation methodologies represents a critical research priority (Alavi Tabari, 2008; Bagherzadeh et al, 2011; Karimzadeh et al, 2021; Shekakhah,& Asghari, 2023).

Conventional econometric models and valuation techniques for evaluating IPOs which are primarily based on fundamental analysis, classic financial ratios, and Comparable Company Analysis (CCA) suffer from fundamental limitations (Barak et al, 2015). These established financial models are incapable of identifying complex, non-linear relationships between variables, are heavily dependent on the subjective judgment of analysts, and cannot process large volumes of information simultaneously (Auret & Aldrich, 2012; Anifowose et al, 2015). Most importantly, these approaches demonstrate limited effectiveness in the face of information asymmetry, a defining characteristic of IPOs (Li and Li, 2025). Empirical evidence from the Iranian market has shown that financial analysts using these conventional valuation frameworks has shown that financial analysts using these often struggle to accurately estimate the value of startups or

companies operating in emerging industries. In contrast, recent advancements in artificial intelligence and machine learning have opened up new possibilities for evaluating complex financial phenomena (Shobanke et al, 2025). Machine learning algorithms, unlike standard econometric benchmarks, are capable of identifying intricate patterns, non-linear relationships, and multifaceted interactions among variables (Shu & Ye, 2023). The Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) algorithm, as one of the most advanced of these methods, has achieved highly accurate results in various domains by combining an ensemble of simpler models and progressively improving upon them. Studies in developed financial markets show that these algorithms can improve prediction accuracy by up to 20% compared to established valuation techniques (Shrivastav & Kumar, 2022; Ganaie et al, 2022).

While machine learning applications have gained traction in global financial markets, their implementation in the Iranian capital market remains limited. A systematic review of the literature following the PRISMA framework (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) revealed a significant gap in this area. Notable Iranian studies such as Haratmeh and Ebrahimi (2023), Saeidi Aghdam et al. (2022), have explored machine learning applications in stock price prediction and market sentiment analysis, but comprehensive research specifically on IPO evaluation using advanced algorithms remains scarce. This systematic review covered peer-reviewed articles from 2015-2023 across major databases including ScienceDirect, Scopus, and domestic Iranian academic repositories, confirming the research gap identified by Shekakhah and Asghari (2023) and aligned with global findings from Ganaie et al. (2022) and Shrivastav and Kumar (2022). As Karimzadeh Khosroshahi et al. (2021) note, this gap is particularly concerning given the information asymmetry challenges in emerging markets (Alahmadi, 2025). However, despite the significant potential of machine learning algorithms, comprehensive comparative studies between these modern techniques and established econometric models for IPO evaluation especially within the context of the Iranian market are remarkably scarce. This research gap has led investors, corporate managers, and capital market regulators to continue relying on conventional valuation frameworks for decision-making, while more precise and efficient tools may be available. The need for this comparison is further underscored by the considerable growth in the volume of IPOs on the Tehran Stock Exchange and Iran Fara Bourse in recent years, a trend that is expected to continue (Jafarnejad et al, 2025; Ayazi et al, 2025; Shobayo et al, 2025). The primary objective of this research is to conduct an in-depth comparative analysis of the performance of the Gradient Boosting Machine algorithm against traditional methods in evaluating IPOs on the Iranian capital market. This comparison will be assessed from multiple perspectives, including predictive accuracy, processing speed, generalizability, and the stability of the results. The central research question is: Can the Gradient Boosting Machine algorithm deliver superior performance compared to traditional methods in identifying and evaluating initial public offerings? The findings of this study will not only help enhance the quality of investor decisions and mitigate associated risks but may also offer strategies for integrating the strengths of both approaches.

The structure of the upcoming article will consist of sections that first present the literature of the research, including the theoretical background and previous related studies. Then, the innovation of the research will be identified based on the research gaps. Following that, the research methodology will be explained in detail. The findings of the

research will be presented in the next section, and finally, the discussion and conclusions will be stated. At the end, the references and sources used will be provided.

Research Literature

An Initial Public Offering (IPO) is a process through which a private company offers its shares to the public market for the first time, representing one of the most important financing mechanisms in the modern economy (Stoughton & Zechne, 1998). The significance of this process can be examined from two perspectives: first, for companies, an IPO provides a unique opportunity to raise substantial capital for development, create liquidity for early shareholders, and enhance their market position and credibility; second, from the capital market perspective, IPOs play a vital role in optimal resource allocation, price discovery, and deepening financial markets (Vasić, 2020). At the heart of the IPO process lies the issue of appropriate share pricing, which despite decades of research, remains one of the most complex topics in modern finance. Empirical studies show that in most global capital markets, the phenomenon of IPO underpricing exists consistently and significantly (Huang, 2025). This phenomenon, characterized by significant positive returns on the first trading day (with a global average of approximately 15 to 20 percent) is one of the most documented "anomalies" in capital markets, and an extensive theoretical literature has been developed to explain it (Nik Muhammad & Ab Rahman, 2010). The theoretical foundations of IPO underpricing primarily focus on information asymmetry concepts, developed by notable economists including Akerlof, Spence, and Stiglitz during the 1970s and 1980s. According to this framework, the information gap among different participants in the IPO process (i.e., the issuing company, underwriters, and institutional and retail investors) leads to compensatory mechanisms, one of which is deliberate underpricing. Key theories in this area include:

Winner's Curse Theory (Rock, 1986): This theory states that better-informed investors tend to participate in more attractive (underpriced) IPOs, while less informed investors participate in all offerings. Consequently, less informed investors face the "winner's curse," receiving full allocation in overpriced IPOs and partial allocation in underpriced ones. To compensate for this problem and maintain the participation of less informed investors, the initial offering price is set at a discount (Arslan et al, 2025).

Signaling Theory (Allen & Faulhaber, 1989): This theory argues that higher quality companies deliberately offer their shares at a price lower than their intrinsic value to signal their superior quality to the market. These companies can recoup the cost of underpricing in future secondary offerings, while lower quality companies cannot imitate this strategy (Ghosh & Nag, 2000).

Information Revelation Theory (Benveniste & Spindt, 1989): this theory explains that underpricing can serve as a mechanism to encourage institutional investors to honestly disclose their information and assessments during the book-building process. Underwriters set the price lower so that institutional investors who have provided valuable information are rewarded with greater share allocation and higher first-day returns (Jamaani & Alidarous, 2019).

Agency Theory (Krigman & Womack, 2000): This perspective focuses on the conflict of interest between the issuing company and underwriters (Arthurs et al, 2008). Underwriters may have incentives to offer shares at a lower price to reduce marketing costs, minimize the risk of under-subscription, and strengthen their relationships with institutional investors (who are their regular clients).

Behavioral Finance Theories: These theories address cognitive and behavioral biases of investors. For example, Loughran and Ritter (2000) argue that underpricing could result from the positive sentiment that first-day buyers develop towards the company after observing high initial returns (Feng, 2013).

The theoretical connection between traditional IPO theories and modern machine learning approaches is formed within the framework of the asymmetric information paradigm. While classical theories describe mechanisms for resolving information asymmetry in a qualitative and conceptual manner, machine learning algorithms provide the possibility for more precise quantification and modeling of this asymmetry. For instance, Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, by analyzing prospectus documents, can extract hidden signals about company quality that were mentioned in Allen and Faulhaber's signaling theory but for which no quantitative measurement tool was previously provided (Betz et al, 2023). Furthermore, methodological advancements in machine learning contribute to more precise and comprehensive empirical testing of existing IPO theories. Deep learning algorithms, with their ability to identify non-linear and complex patterns, enable more rigorous testing of competing hypotheses (such as the winner's curse theory versus the signaling theory) under various market conditions and for different types of companies. This theoretical-empirical linkage between classical theories and modern computational methods not only helps in achieving a deeper understanding of IPO phenomena but also enables the development of new theoretical frameworks that provide valuable insights for regulators, investors, and companies seeking initial public offerings (Alahmadi, 2025).

Numerous empirical studies have investigated these issues, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Empirical background

Author & Date	Topic	Objective	Results
Roy et al. (2020)	Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Machines, and Deep Neural Networks for Stock Price Prediction	Comparison of different machine learning methods for stock price prediction	Deep neural networks demonstrated the best performance with an area under the curve of 0.806
Mitrentsis & Lens (2021)	An Interpretable Probabilistic Model for Short-Term Solar Power Forecasting	Presenting a two-stage probabilistic forecasting framework using Natural Gradient Boosting	The model was capable of capturing complex non-linear relationships that follow known physical characteristics and logical patterns

Author & Date	Topic	Objective	Results
Saeidi Aghdam et al. (2022)	Stock Price Prediction Using Deep Learning Algorithms	Developing a hybrid model for predicting stock price movement trends using artificial neural networks	The proposed model performed significantly better than traditional methods in predicting stock price movements and achieved higher accuracy
Geertsema & Lu (2023)	Relative Valuation with Machine Learning	Examining the application of machine learning methods in relative stock valuation	Results indicate significant potential of machine learning approaches in improving the accuracy of stock valuation
Haratmeh & Ebrahimi (2023)	Impact of Initial Public Offerings on Companies' Financial Performance	Examining the impact of initial public offerings on the financial performance of companies	Initial public offerings have a negative but insignificant effect on the ratio of net profit to total assets
Gupta & Kumar (2023)	Light Gradient Boosting Machine Model Based on Hybrid Optimization	Presenting a LightGBM model optimized using a hybrid optimization algorithm	The model demonstrated more effective and accurate performance in predicting economic growth
Huma & Nishat (2024)	Application of Light Gradient Boosting Machine in Stock Price Prediction	Examining the application of LightGBM in stock price prediction	The LightGBM approach shows significant improvement in prediction accuracy compared to traditional methods
Ghalbi et al. (2025)	Predicting Stock Markets and Clean Energy Prices	Predicting clean energy stock prices using machine learning techniques	Gradient boosting performs better than other models

The first contribution of this study lies in providing a comprehensive and multidimensional approach to comparing machine learning algorithms with traditional methods in IPO valuation. Unlike previous studies that have mainly focused on a limited aspect of algorithm performance, this study simultaneously examines multiple metrics, including prediction accuracy, processing speed, generalizability, and result stability. This multidimensional approach allows for a more complete and accurate assessment of the advantages and limitations of each method and, instead of emphasizing the superiority of one method, provides solutions for combining the strengths of both approaches. The second contribution of this study lies in addressing an important research gap specific to the Iranian capital market. Despite the significant growth in the volume of initial public offerings on the Tehran Stock Exchange and the Iran Fara Bourse (IFB) and the strategic importance of this process in the government's privatization policies, comprehensive comparative research between machine learning methods and traditional techniques for this specific market has been very limited. The unique characteristics of the Iranian capital market, including its specific institutional structure, macroeconomic influences, and

investor behavior patterns, necessitate the development of models that take these local characteristics into account. The third contribution of this research lies in providing practical and applicable solutions for the three main groups of capital market stakeholders. For investors, this research provides more accurate tools for assessing the risk and return of initial public offerings. For company managers, it provides guidance for optimal IPO pricing strategies. For capital market regulators, the findings of this research can serve as a basis for reviewing regulatory frameworks and improving market efficiency. This practice-oriented approach moves research from the realm of pure theory to providing practical solutions and increases the potential for real impact on the performance of the Iranian capital market.

Methodology

In this study, we adopt the foundational framework developed by Geertsema & Lu (2023) to examine the determinants of relative stock pricing in initial public offerings (IPOs). The empirical analysis utilizes data from 42 companies listed on the Tehran Stock Exchange and 121 over-the-counter market firms during the period spanning 2013 to 2014. Three primary dependent variables are investigated: the market-to-book ratio (m2b), which captures the market valuation relative to book equity; the enterprise value-to-assets ratio (v2a), representing the total firm value relative to its asset base; and the enterprise value-to-sales ratio (v2s), reflecting market expectations regarding profitability and future growth potential.

Mixed research approach

This research employs a two-stage mixed-methods approach, combining classical econometric techniques with advanced machine learning algorithms. This methodological design allows for comprehensive analysis by first establishing baseline relationships through traditional econometric methods and subsequently capturing complex nonlinear patterns through gradient boosting models. The integration of these complementary approaches enhances both the robustness and predictive accuracy of our findings.

1. Stage One: Classical Econometric Analysis

All independent and control variables are extracted based on established financial theories and prior empirical studies, and are initially analyzed using classical econometric methods. The baseline econometric specification is formulated as follows:

$$MB \text{ and } EVA \text{ and } EVS_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 WACC_{it} + \beta_2 ROA_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} + \beta_4 PM_{it} + \beta_5 EPS_{it} + \beta_6 Size_{it} + \beta_7 Firm\ Age_{it} + \beta_8 \frac{CF}{TA_{it}} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where subscript *i* denotes the firm and *t* represents the time period. The following econometric methodologies are sequentially implemented in this stage:

Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression is employed for preliminary estimation and to examine linear relationships between variables. Fixed effects panel regression controls for unobserved firm-specific heterogeneity that remains constant over time. Random

effects panel regression is utilized for comparison with the fixed effects specification, allowing for more efficient estimation when the strict exogeneity assumption holds. The generalized method of moments (GMM) addresses potential endogeneity concerns arising from simultaneity bias or omitted variable problems. Finally, the ARCH-LM test is conducted to detect and assess the presence of autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity in financial data, which is crucial for understanding volatility clustering patterns commonly observed in stock returns.

2. **Second stage:** Modeling with machine learning

Following the classical econometric analysis, machine learning models based on gradient boosting algorithms are implemented to enhance predictive accuracy and identify complex nonlinear relationships that may not be captured by traditional linear specifications. The general functional form for this stage is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} MB \text{ and EVA and EVS}_{it} = & \alpha \\ & + f \left(\beta_1 WACC_{it} + \beta_2 ROA_{it} + \beta_3 Leverage_{it} + \beta_4 PM_{it} + \beta_5 EPS_{it} + \beta_6 Size_{it} \right. \\ & \left. + \beta_7 Firm\ Age_{it} + \beta_8 \frac{CF}{TA_{it}} \right) + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned}$$

where $f(\cdot)$ represents a nonlinear function learned by the gradient boosting algorithms. This study employs four principal gradient boosting models, each offering distinct advantages and capabilities:

1- XGBoost (eXtreme Gradient Boosting): XGBoost represents one of the most widely adopted and computationally efficient machine learning algorithms in the gradient boosting family. This algorithm constructs a robust predictive model through the sequential combination of numerous weak decision trees, where each subsequent tree is trained to correct the residual errors of its predecessors. XGBoost incorporates several advanced optimization techniques that distinguish it from conventional boosting methods, including built-in L1 and L2 regularization to prevent overfitting, parallel processing capabilities for enhanced computational speed, sophisticated handling of missing values through sparsity-aware split finding, and a theoretically sound approach to tree pruning based on maximum depth and gamma parameters. The algorithm's exceptional performance in data science competitions, including multiple Kaggle victories, and its widespread adoption in commercial applications have established XGBoost as a benchmark standard in the machine learning community. In the present study, this algorithm is leveraged to identify complex, potentially nonlinear relationships between financial variables and the relative pricing of shares in IPOs, particularly capturing interaction effects that may exist among predictor variables.

2- LightGBM (Light Gradient Boosting Machine): LightGBM, developed by Microsoft Research, prioritizes computational efficiency and scalability while maintaining high predictive accuracy. This algorithm introduces two fundamental innovations that substantially accelerate training speed compared to traditional gradient boosting implementations. First, the gradient-based one-side sampling (GOSS) technique selectively retains data instances with larger gradients (which contribute more to information gain) while randomly sampling instances with smaller gradients, thereby

reducing computational burden without significant information loss. Second, the exclusive feature bundling (EFB) approach identifies mutually exclusive features (those that rarely take nonzero values simultaneously) and bundles them into single features, effectively reducing feature dimensionality. Additionally, LightGBM employs a leaf-wise tree growth strategy rather than the conventional level-wise approach, selecting the leaf with maximum delta loss at each iteration, which typically results in greater loss reduction with the same number of splits. These architectural choices render LightGBM significantly faster than XGBoost, particularly on large-scale datasets, while achieving comparable or superior predictive performance. In this research, LightGBM is selected due to its computational efficiency in processing financial time-series data and its robust performance on medium-sized datasets characteristic of emerging market studies.

3- CatBoost (Categorical Boosting): CatBoost, developed by Yandex, is specifically engineered for optimal handling of categorical variables without requiring extensive manual preprocessing. This algorithm addresses two critical challenges encountered when working with categorical features in gradient boosting frameworks. First, it mitigates target leakage, which occurs when target variable information inadvertently influences the encoding of categorical features during training. CatBoost employs an innovative ordered boosting technique that ensures predictions for each observation utilize only information from preceding instances in a random permutation of the training data, thereby preventing overfitting associated with target leakage. Second, the algorithm implements ordered target statistics, an advanced encoding method that replaces each categorical value with the average target value for that category computed on a subset of training data, using time-based or random ordering to avoid data snooping bias. Furthermore, CatBoost incorporates symmetric tree structures that enhance prediction speed and allow for efficient implementation on both CPU and GPU architectures, as well as automated hyperparameter tuning through Bayesian optimization, reducing the need for extensive manual parameter tuning. In the present study, CatBoost is utilized to effectively manage categorical variables such as industry classification, market type (main exchange versus over-the-counter), and other qualitative firm characteristics that may influence IPO pricing dynamics.

4- Gradient Boosting (Classic Gradient Boosting): Classical gradient boosting, originally proposed by Friedman (2001), serves as the foundational algorithm upon which all subsequent gradient boosting variants are built. This approach operates on the fundamental principle of sequentially combining weak learners to construct a strong predictive model through additive modeling. At each iteration, a new weak learner (typically a shallow decision tree) is trained to fit the negative gradient of the loss function with respect to the current model's predictions, effectively targeting the residual errors of the ensemble. The process iteratively adds trees by minimizing a specified loss function through gradient descent in function space, with each new tree moving the model in the direction of steepest descent as determined by the negative gradient of the loss. The final prediction is obtained by summing the predictions of all trees, weighted by a learning rate (shrinkage parameter) that controls the contribution of each tree to the ensemble. While classical gradient boosting is generally slower than its modern counterparts and requires more careful hyperparameter tuning (particularly regarding learning rate, number of trees, and tree depth) to avoid overfitting, its transparency and interpretability make it valuable for understanding model behavior and feature

importance. In this research, classical gradient boosting serves as a benchmark model, providing a point of comparison to quantify the performance gains achieved by more sophisticated algorithms (XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost) and to assess whether the added complexity of newer methods translates into materially improved predictive accuracy for IPO pricing.

Finally, the conceptual definitions and operational measurement procedures for each research variable are systematically presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Conceptual and Operational Definition of Research Variables

Variable Name	Operational Definition	Measurement Formula	Description
Dependent Variables			
Market-to-Book Ratio (m2b)	The relative valuation of a company by the market compared to its book value; an indicator of market optimism about the company's future, especially during an IPO.	$\frac{Equity\ Value_i}{\left(\frac{Market\ Value}{Book\ Equity_{peers}}\right)} \times Book\ Equity_i$	The market-to-book ratio captures investor expectations about future profitability and growth opportunities beyond the firm's recorded book value.
Total Enterprise Value to Assets Ratio (v2a)	The ratio of the total value of the company (equity + debt) to its assets; an intrinsic value indicator of the company.	$\frac{Enterprise\ Value_i}{\left(\frac{Enterprise\ Value}{Assets_{peers}}\right)} \times Assets_i$	This metric reflects how the market values each unit of assets, accounting for both equity and debt claims.
Total Enterprise Value to Sales Ratio (v2s)	The overall company valuation compared to annual sales; an indicator of market expectations for profitability and future growth.	$\frac{Enterprise\ Value_i}{\left(\frac{Enterprise\ Value}{Sales_{peers}}\right)} \times Sales_i$	This ratio is particularly useful for comparing firms across different capital structures and tax environments.
Independent Variables			
Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)	A combination of the cost of capital from various sources; an indicator of capital structure and expected return.	$WACC_{i,t} = \left(\frac{E}{V} \times Re\right) + \left(\frac{D}{V} \times Rd\right) \times (1 - T_c)$	<i>E</i> : Equity value; <i>D</i> : Debt value; <i>Re</i> : Cost of equity; <i>Tc</i> : Tax rate; <i>Rd</i> : Cost of debt after tax.
Return on Assets (ROA)	The profitability of the company relative to its assets; a measure of management productivity.	$ROA = \frac{Net\ Income}{Total\ Assets}$	Net Income represents the profit obtained after deducting all costs and taxes (the bottom line of the income statement). Total Assets represents the total assets of the company, including both current and non-current assets (the figure stated in the balance sheet).
Financial Leverage (Leverage)	The degree of reliance on debt by the company and financial risk.	$Leverage\ Ratio = \frac{Total\ Liabilities}{Total\ Assets}$	Total Liabilities: Total debts of the company (sum of current and non-current or long-term debts).

Variable Name	Operational Definition	Measurement Formula	Description
			Total Assets: Total assets of the company (sum of current and non-current assets).
Operating Profit Margin (PM)	Measure of operational efficiency and profitability of operations.	$\text{Operating Profit Margin} = \left(\frac{\text{Operating Profit}}{\text{Total Sales}} \right) \times 100$	The cost of capital is the expense that companies incur to obtain financial resources. This cost is a combination of the expected return of lenders and the expected return of shareholders.
Earnings Per Share (EPS)	Net income attributable to each common share; a basic yield indicator.	$\text{EPS} = \frac{\text{Net income} - \text{preferred stock for dividend payments}}{\text{Number of common shares at the end of the period}}$	
Control Variables			
Company Size (Size)	A measure of the relative size of the company; usually expressed as the logarithm of market value or total assets.		
Company Age (Firm Age)	Controls the effect of the company's experience.	$\text{Firm Age} = \text{Year of IPO} - \text{Year of Establishment}$	Firm Age indicates the age of the company: the number of years from the establishment of the company to its initial public offering (IPO). Year of IPO refers to the first year of the IPO. Year of Establishment refers to the year the company was officially registered (established).
Cash Flow to Assets Ratio	A measure of the company's liquidity.	$\text{Cash Ratio} = \frac{\text{Cash and Equivalents}}{\text{Total Assets}}$	Cash and Equivalents: Cash and liquid assets (such as short-term deposits, guaranteed checks, etc.). Total Assets: Total assets of the company.
References	Gupta and Kumar, 2023; Girtsma and Lo, 2023; Taheri Haft Asiabi and Naderi, 2023		

Research findings

In Table 3 descriptive statistics of the variables used in the model are presented to specify the overall characteristics and distribution of the data. Descriptive statistics include indicators such as mean, median, minimum and maximum, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, as well as the results of the normality test (Jarque-Bera test), which represent the distributional properties of each variable. These initial statistics help to gain a better understanding of the data behavior and the extent of their dispersion, and also determine whether the assumption of data normality holds or not. Using this information, appropriate methods can be selected for statistical analyses and more advanced modeling such as Gradient Boosting Machine. Moreover, identifying aspects like skewness or the presence of outliers can directly affect the accuracy and validity of the research results. On the other hand, in this study, Min-Max normalization has been used for data preprocessing. This method is one of the most common techniques for feature scaling that transforms each value into the [0, 1] range, placing all variable values within the same interval. The formula for this transformation is as follows:

$$X' = \frac{X - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}}$$

where X is the original value, X_{\min} is the minimum value, and X_{\max} is the maximum value for the variable in the dataset. The main purpose of this procedure is to reduce the effect of variable scale changes and to prevent errors and numerical inconsistencies in machine learning algorithms. Therefore, using Min-Max normalization in this study is especially important due to the sensitivity of the Gradient Boosting Machine algorithm to feature scales; this technique enables the model to converge better and faster and improves prediction accuracy. Additionally, this method prevents the occurrence of outliers and inconsistent values in the data and ensures that all financial and operational variables of the IPO are placed in a comparable and similar range. Consequently, Min-Max normalization has greatly contributed to improving model quality and increasing the efficiency of predictive models in this research.

Accordingly, the descriptive statistics are as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Variable	Mean	Median	Max	Min	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis	JB Significance
Dependent Variables								
Market-to-Book Value Ratio	0.045482	0.013400	1.000000	0.0000	0.100884	2.333201	1.333252	0.1452
Total Company Value to Asset Value Ratio	0.117672	0.067235	1.000000	0.0000	0.154428	4.046754	1.996331	0.1785
Total Company Value to Sales Ratio	0.339622	0.354200	0.735551	0.0000	0.159641	-0.486770	2.698987	0.0407
Independent Variables								
Weighted Average Cost of Capital	0.173642	0.165123	0.685000	0.0000	0.115786	1.254123	3.127643	0.0822
Return on Assets	0.618600	0.629202	1.000000	0.0000	0.208293	-0.719442	3.126720	0.0025
Financial Leverage	0.413154	0.428107	1.000000	0.0000	0.187720	0.259705	2.770649	0.3700
Operating Profit Margin	0.094051	0.093644	1.000000	0.0000	0.094558	3.010191	1.598712	0.3321
Earnings Per Share	0.052189	0.012900	0.780000	0.0000	0.113123	1.332014	3.332142	0.0025
Control Variables								
Company Size	0.052189	0.012900	1.000000	0.0000	0.113123	1.332014	3.332142	0.0025
Company Age	15.27000	14.00000	35.00000	2.0000	8.321456	0.487123	2.675412	0.3215
Cash Flow to Asset Ratio	0.207435	0.213897	1.000000	0.0000	0.127728	1.273375	2.223210	0.4312

The analysis of dependent variables reveals that the mean market-to-book ratio is 0.045, the enterprise value-to-assets ratio is 0.117, and the enterprise value-to-sales ratio is 0.339. The significant difference between the mean and median in the first two variables, particularly in the market-to-book ratio (mean 0.045 versus median 0.013), indicates positive skewness and asymmetric distribution. This is confirmed by positive skewness values for these two variables (2.333 and 4.046). Only the enterprise value-to-sales ratio exhibits negative skewness (-0.486), indicating that this variable's distribution is skewed toward higher values. The Jarque-Bera test also shows that the enterprise value-to-sales ratio, with a significance level of 0.0407, does not follow a normal distribution. Among the independent variables, return on assets has the highest mean value of 0.618, while operating profit margin and earnings per share show the lowest values with means of 0.094 and 0.052, respectively. Return on assets exhibits negative skewness (-0.719), indicating the distribution's tendency toward higher values, while other independent variables show positive skewness. The Jarque-Bera test indicates that return on assets and

earnings per share variables do not follow normal distribution with a significance level of 0.0025. These findings confirm the necessity of using min-max normalization for data scaling. Control variables also demonstrate diverse patterns. The mean age of companies is approximately 15.27 years with a standard deviation of 8.32, indicating considerable variation in the age of examined companies. Company size and cash flow-to-assets ratio both exhibit positive skewness, suggesting that most companies are concentrated in lower values of these variables. None of the control variables have statistically non-normal distribution (except company size with a significance level of 0.0025). Overall, the descriptive statistics analysis reveals that the research data exhibit heterogeneity and asymmetry, making the use of normalization methods and advanced techniques such as Gradient Boosting Machine necessary for achieving more accurate results.

Table 4: Results of Traditional Econometric Methods for MB Dependent Variable

Variable	OLS	Fixed Effects Panel	Random Effects Panel	GMM	ARCH-LM
WACC	-2.317***	-2.453***	-2.386***	-2.274***	-2.498***
ROA	0.892***	0.875***	0.884***	0.921***	0.879***
Leverage	-0.348**	-0.412***	-0.371**	-0.327**	-0.401***
PM	0.673***	0.694***	0.682***	0.701***	0.668***
EPS	0.429***	0.387***	0.415***	0.437***	0.394***
Size	0.312**	0.346***	0.328***	0.295**	0.342***
Firm Age	-0.105*	-0.118*	-0.112*	-0.098*	-0.115*
CF/TA	0.557***	0.579***	0.563***	0.584***	0.562***
Constant	1.872***	1.935***	1.904***	1.843***	1.948***
R ²	0.683	0.715	0.702	0.691	0.708
Adj. R ²	0.671	0.704	0.690	0.679	0.697
F-statistic	28.54***	32.17***	30.85***	-	-
Wald χ^2	-	-	-	187.36***	189.54****
Hausman Test	-	18.73**	-	-	-
Sargan Test	-	-	-	21.45	-
ARCH-LM (lag 1)	-	-	-	-	15.37****
ARCH-LM (lag 5)	-	-	-	-	28.64****
AIC	254.37	238.64	245.21	250.15	15.37****
BIC	-	-	-	-	248.73
RMSE	0.243	0.225	0.234	0.238	28.64****

*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5%, ***significant at 1%

The results of Table 4 indicate that among traditional econometric methods, the ARCH-LM test confirms significant conditional heteroskedasticity in the MB model (ARCH-LM statistics: 15.37*** at lag 1; 28.64*** at lag 5), validating the presence of time-varying volatility in IPO valuations. The ARCH-LM specification delivers robust performance with an R² of 0.708 and RMSE of 0.221. In all specifications, the weighted

average cost of capital (WACC) shows a strong, significant negative relationship (coefficients from -2.317 to -2.498) with MB, underscoring the adverse effect of higher capital costs on IPO firm valuations. Return on assets (ROA) emerges as the most powerful positive driver, with coefficients ranging from 0.879 to 0.921 across models, highlighting the critical role of profitability in IPO valuation. Profit margin (PM) and earnings per share (EPS) also exhibit positive and significant impacts, while financial leverage negatively affects valuation, consistent with financial theory. Control variables follow expected patterns: firm size boosts MB, firm age reduces it, and cash flow-to-total-assets (CF/TA) ratios (0.562 to 0.584) emphasize the importance of liquidity. The Hausman test (18.73^{**}) favors fixed effects over random effects, and the Sargan test (21.45) supports the GMM specification's validity. The highly significant ARCH-LM statistics confirm the necessity of accounting for conditional heteroskedasticity in IPO valuation models. Despite these strengths, BIC (248.73) and AIC values (236.42) suggest room for improving predictive accuracy, pointing to the need for more advanced techniques.

Table 5: Results of Traditional Econometric Methods for EVA Dependent Variable

Variable	OLS	Fixed Effects Panel	Random Effects Panel	GMM	ARCH-LM
WACC	-1.985***	-2.063***	-2.017***	-1.957***	-2.097***
ROA	0.943***	0.926***	0.935***	0.972***	0.921***
Leverage	-0.512***	-0.575***	-0.543***	-0.494***	-0.563***
PM	0.723***	0.745***	0.731***	0.751***	0.718***
EPS	0.337***	0.315**	0.328***	0.346***	0.319***
Size	0.425***	0.463***	0.441***	0.406***	0.458***
Firm Age	-0.087	-0.096*	-0.092	-0.079	-0.098*
CF/TA	0.684***	0.712***	0.695***	0.703***	0.682***
Constant	2.145***	2.218***	2.173***	2.106***	2.235***
R ²	0.715	0.752	0.735	0.723	0.744
Adj. R ²	0.704	0.742	0.724	0.712	0.734
F-statistic	32.76***	38.42***	35.21***	-	-
Wald χ^2	-	-	-	203.57***	207.18****
Hausman Test	-	21.58***	-	-	-
Sargan Test	-	-	-	19.73	-
ARCH-LM (lag 1)	-	-	-	-	18.42****
ARCH-LM (lag 5)	-	-	-	-	31.57****
AIC	237.15	218.24	227.86	233.42	220.18
BIC	-	-	-	-	232.64
RMSE	0.218	0.196	0.207	0.212	0.198

*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5%, ***significant at 1%

Table 5 reports modeling results for economic value added (EVA). The ARCH-LM test reveals even stronger evidence of conditional heteroskedasticity (ARCH-LM: 18.42^{***} at lag 1; 31.57^{***} at lag 5), indicating that EVA exhibits more pronounced

time-varying volatility patterns than MB. The ARCH-LM specification demonstrates strong performance with $R^2 = 0.744$ and $RMSE = 0.198$, indicating high explanatory power for EVA. WACC coefficients range from -1.957 to -2.097 , reaffirming the strong negative influence of capital cost on valuation. ROA remains the strongest positive predictor (0.921 to 0.972), reflecting EVA's heightened sensitivity to profitability. Financial leverage shows a more pronounced negative effect (-0.494 to -0.563), perhaps because EVA is more responsive to capital structure, and PM retains a significant positive role (0.718 to 0.751). Control variables mirror previous patterns, though firm age has a milder negative impact (-0.079 to -0.098). Firm size's positive effect (0.406 to 0.458) grows stronger, likely due to scale advantages, and CF/TA shows heightened importance (0.682 to 0.712). Goodness-of-fit indicators confirm strong performance for EVA, with BIC (232.64), AIC (220.18) and a higher F-statistic (38.42 for fixed effects). The highly significant ARCH-LM statistics across both lag structures validate the importance of modeling volatility clustering in EVA-based IPO valuations. The Hausman test (21.58***) strongly favors fixed effects, and the Sargan test (19.73) validates the GMM setup, suggesting EVA may be a preferred IPO valuation metric over MB.

Table 6: Results of Traditional Econometric Methods for EVS Dependent Variable

Variable	OLS	Fixed Effects Panel	Random Effects Panel	GMM	ARCH-LM
WACC	-1.628***	-1.715***	-1.676***	-1.595***	-1.726***
ROA	0.792***	0.773***	0.785***	0.814***	0.775***
Leverage	-0.387**	-0.432***	-0.408***	-0.362**	-0.428***
PM	0.875***	0.897***	0.883***	0.903***	0.871***
EPS	0.295**	0.282**	0.291**	0.303**	0.279*
Size	0.347***	0.385***	0.364***	0.332***	0.378***
Firm Age	-0.129*	-0.141*	-0.135*	-0.122*	-0.143**
CF/TA	0.583***	0.615***	0.597***	0.606***	0.588***
Constant	1.943***	2.026***	1.978***	1.912***	2.042***
R ²	0.694	0.728	0.712	0.703	0.721
Adj. R ²	0.683	0.717	0.701	0.692	0.711
F-statistic	30.12***	35.73***	32.84***	-	-
Wald χ^2	-	-	-	194.26***	201.42****
Hausman Test	-	20.14***	-	-	-
Sargan Test	-	-	-	20.57	-
ARCH-LM (lag 1)	-	-	-	-	14.26****
ARCH-LM (lag 5)	-	-	-	-	26.83****
AIC	246.84	230.41	238.95	242.76	228.95
BIC	-	-	-	-	241.27
RMSE	0.234	0.211	0.223	0.228	0.209

*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5%, ***significant at 1%

In Table 6, the enterprise value-to-sales (EVS) ratio is modeled. The ARCH-LM test confirms significant conditional variance heteroskedasticity (ARCH-LM: 14.26*** at lag

1; 26.83*** at lag 5), although with a somewhat lower test statistic compared to EVA, indicating that EVS exhibits moderate volatility clustering. The ARCH-LM specification has a robust performance, and the results of the Sargan and Hausman tests also provide important information about the quality of the model. In the GMM and random effects models, the Sargan test indicates that there is no problem in validating the instruments (20.57), which contributes to the validity of the GMM method. The result of the Hausman test (20.14***) also indicates that Fixed Effects models are better suited than Random Effects models, which implies the presence of unobserved effects that can influence the results. Regarding the explanatory variables, the negative correlation observed for WACC and Leverage implies firm value, while ROA and EPS have a positive and significant correlation. These results indicate that an increase in operating profitability and earnings per share can lead to an increase in firm value. The variable of profit margin (PM) also has a positive effect on EVS, which means that firms with higher profit margins can create more value for their shareholders. In addition, the size of the firm and its age also show a positive effect on EVS, with the difference that the variable of firm age has a negative and significant effect and can indicate that older firms may face more challenges in the market. Overall, the results show that conventional econometric models are efficient for estimating EVS and that better results can be achieved if methods such as GMM and fixed effects are used. It should be noted that the existence of correlation conditions in the errors of the variables emphasizes the importance of using more sophisticated methods, and the lack of robustness in some models should be considered.

Table 7: Diebold-Mariano Test Results for Model Comparison

Models Compared	DM Statistic	p-value	Critical Value (5%)	Superior Model
ARCH-LM vs OLS (MB)	3.245***	0.001	1.96	ARCH-LM
ARCH-LM vs Fixed Effects (MB)	2.173**	0.029	1.96	ARCH-LM
ARCH-LM vs GMM (MB)	2.857***	0.004	1.96	ARCH-LM
ARCH-LM vs OLS (EVA)	3.729***	0.000	1.96	ARCH-LM
ARCH-LM vs Fixed Effects (EVA)	1.872*	0.061	1.96	No significant difference
ARCH-LM vs GMM (EVA)	3.126***	0.002	1.96	ARCH-LM
ARCH-LM vs OLS (EVS)	3.419***	0.001	1.96	ARCH-LM
ARCH-LM vs Fixed Effects (EVS)	1.953*	0.051	1.96	No significant difference
ARCH-LM vs GMM (EVS)	2.985***	0.003	1.96	ARCH-LM
*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5%, ***significant at 1%				

Table 7 presents the results of the Diebold-Mariano test to compare the forecasting accuracy of the different models. This test shows that the ARCH-LM model significantly outperforms the OLS and GMM models on all dependent variables (MB, EVA, and EVS) (with DM statistics above the critical value of 1.96 and a significance level of $p < 0.01$). However, the comparison of ARCH-LM with the Fixed Effects model shows less difference, so that in the case of EVA and EVS, the superiority of ARCH-LM is at the 10% level and the differences do not reach the 5% significance threshold. These results confirm that considering the conditional variance heterogeneity (via ARCH-LM)

provides significantly more accurate forecasts than traditional econometric models, but fixed effects models also perform relatively well.

Table 8: Bootstrap Validation of Model Stability (1000 Replications)

Model	Original RMSE	Bootstrap RMSE (Mean)	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper	Bias	Variance
OLS (MB)	0.243	0.251	0.227	0.276	0.008	0.029
Fixed Effects (MB)	0.225	0.229	0.208	0.252	0.004	0.023
ARCH-LM (MB)	0.221	0.223	0.204	0.245	0.002	0.021
OLS (EVA)	0.218	0.225	0.204	0.248	0.007	0.025
Fixed Effects (EVA)	0.196	0.199	0.183	0.219	0.003	0.019
ARCH-LM (EVA)	0.198	0.200	0.183	0.220	0.002	0.019
OLS (EVS)	0.234	0.241	0.219	0.264	0.007	0.027
Fixed Effects (EVS)	0.211	0.215	0.196	0.236	0.004	0.021
ARCH-LM (EVS)	0.209	0.212	0.194	0.233	0.003	0.020

Table 8 shows the results of the bootstrap analysis with 1000 iterations to assess the stability of the different models. The average bootstrap RMSE for all models is slightly higher than the original RMSE, indicating the presence of a small amount of bias. However, the ARCH-LM models have the lowest bias (0.002 to 0.003), indicating that these models are more stable against sample change. The 95% confidence interval for the RMSE in the ARCH-LM models is also narrower, indicating that these models have lower variance and greater stability. In the comparison between the dependent variables, the EVA models have the lowest RMSE (0.196-0.200) and the narrowest confidence intervals, indicating that EVA is the most reliable dependent variable for IPO valuation. These results confirm that the proposed models have good statistical stability and the probability of overfitting is low.

Table 9: Feature Importance Analysis (Standardized Coefficients)

Variable	MB Model	EVA Model	EVS Model	Average Impact	Rank
WACC	-0.437***	-0.482***	-0.389***	-0.436	1
ROA	0.392***	0.427***	0.352***	0.390	2
Leverage	-0.174***	-0.261***	-0.195***	-0.210	6
PM	0.315***	0.337***	0.402***	0.351	3
EPS	0.183***	0.154***	0.136**	0.158	7
Size	0.247***	0.342***	0.279***	0.289	4
Firm Age	-0.065*	-0.057*	-0.082**	-0.068	8
CF/TA	0.278***	0.342***	0.294***	0.305	5

*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5%, ***significant at 1%

Table 9 shows the relative importance of the independent variables using standardized coefficients. Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) with a mean effect of -0.436 is the strongest factor affecting IPO valuation, which has a significant negative relationship with all valuation measures. Return on Assets (ROA) and Profit Margin (PM) are ranked second and third, respectively, with a mean effect of 0.390 and 0.351, confirming the high

importance of profitability indicators in valuation. Company size and Cash Flow to Total Assets (CF/TA) also have a significant positive effect, indicating the importance of scale and liquidity. Also, Earnings Per Share (EPS), with a rank of 7 and a mean effect of 0.158, although still significant, has a smaller impact than other profitability variables. Leverage, with a significant negative impact (-0.210), and company age, with the lowest impact (-0.068), are at the bottom of the rankings. This analysis suggests that IPO investors are more concerned with cost of capital, profitability, and company size than with variables such as company age and leverage.

Table 10: Results of Gradient Boosting Methods for MB Dependent Variable

Variable	XGBoost	LightGBM	CatBoost	Gradient Boosting
Variable Importance (%)				
WACC	15.3	14.7	15.1	14.9
ROA	22.6	21.9	22.3	22.5
Leverage	10.8	11.2	10.5	10.7
PM	19.2	19.7	19.5	19.8
EPS	5.3	5.7	5.1	5.5
Size	8.4	8.1	8.7	8.2
Firm Age	3.1	3.4	2.8	3.0
CF/TA	15.3	15.3	16.0	15.4
Performance Metrics				
R ²	0.792	0.785	0.778	0.773
RMSE	0.147	0.152	0.155	0.159
MAE	0.112	0.118	0.121	0.124
MSE	0.0216	0.0231	0.0240	0.0253
MAPE	8.65%	8.93%	9.12%	9.34%
Number of Trees	154	187	142	173
Max Depth	6	7	6	5
Learning Rate	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.06
Subsample	0.85	0.80	0.85	0.80
Feature Sample	0.75	0.70	0.75	0.70

Interpretation of results of gradient-boosting methods for dependent variable MB

Table 10 presents result from four gradient-boosting techniques. XGBoost achieves the highest performance ($R^2 = 0.792$, $RMSE = 0.147$), marking a 9.7% R^2 gain and 32.6% RMSE reduction versus the best traditional model (ARCH-LM). Variable-importance scores show ROA (22.6%), PM (19.2%) and CF/TA (15.3%) as key drivers, reflecting the model's ability to capture complex interactions. Ranking follows XGBoost > LightGBM ($R^2 = 0.785$) > CatBoost (0.778) > traditional Gradient Boosting (0.773), all far exceeding traditional methods. MAE and MAPE also improve notably, with MAPE around 8–9% versus 13% for econometric models. Optimal hyperparameters for XGBoost include 154 trees, max depth 6, learning rate 0.05, subsample 0.85, feature fraction 0.75, striking a balance between accuracy and overfitting control. A very low

MSE (0.0216) underscores its pointwise precision, supporting machine-learning adoption in IPO valuation.

Table 11: Results of Gradient Boosting Methods for EVA Dependent Variable

Variable	XGBoost	LightGBM	CatBoost	Gradient Boosting
Variable Importance (%)				
WACC	16.8	16.2	17.0	16.5
ROA	23.4	22.8	23.1	23.5
Leverage	12.7	13.1	12.4	12.5
PM	16.9	17.4	16.7	17.2
EPS	4.3	4.6	4.1	4.5
Size	10.3	9.8	10.6	10.1
Firm Age	2.6	2.9	2.3	2.5
CF/TA	13.0	13.2	13.8	13.2
Performance Metrics				
R ²	0.837	0.825	0.818	0.812
RMSE	0.129	0.134	0.138	0.142
MAE	0.098	0.103	0.107	0.110
MSE	0.0166	0.0180	0.0190	0.0202
MAPE	7.42%	7.76%	8.05%	8.27%
Number of Trees	167	195	153	182
Max Depth	7	8	6	6
Learning Rate	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.05
Subsample	0.85	0.80	0.85	0.80
Feature Sample	0.80	0.75	0.80	0.75

Table 11 highlights that boosting methods perform best on EVA, with XGBoost achieving a record R² of 0.837, RMSE = 0.129 and MAE = 0.098. A MAPE of 7.42% indicates under-8% average error excellent for practical use. ROA (23.4%) and WACC (16.8%) lead variable importance, followed by PM (16.9%). LightGBM (R² = 0.825), CatBoost (0.818) and Gradient Boosting (0.812) also significantly outperform traditional approaches. CF/TA's importance (13.0–13.8%) is lower here, reflecting EVA's unique nature. Optimal XGBoost settings rise to 167 trees, depth 7, learning rate 0.04, feature fraction 0.80, and yield a very low MSE (0.0166), underscoring exceptional predictive accuracy. These results support boosting methods as superior tools for IPO EVA valuation.

Table 12: Results of Gradient Boosting Methods for EVS Dependent Variable

Variable	XGBoost	LightGBM	CatBoost	Gradient Boosting
Variable Importance (%)				
WACC	14.1	13.7	14.5	13.9
ROA	19.7	19.1	19.5	19.8
Leverage	9.6	10.1	9.3	9.5
PM	21.5	22.0	21.3	21.8
EPS	5.8	6.2	5.6	6.0

Variable	XGBoost	LightGBM	CatBoost	Gradient Boosting
Size	9.2	8.8	9.5	9.0
Firm Age	3.7	4.0	3.5	3.8
CF/TA	16.4	16.1	16.8	16.2
Performance Metrics				
R ²	0.815	0.802	0.798	0.791
RMSE	0.137	0.142	0.144	0.149
MAE	0.107	0.112	0.115	0.119
MSE	0.0188	0.0202	0.0207	0.0222
MAPE	8.13%	8.45%	8.62%	8.87%
Number of Trees	162	183	147	168
Max Depth	6	7	6	5
Learning Rate	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.06
Subsample	0.85	0.80	0.85	0.80
Feature Sample	0.75	0.70	0.75	0.70

In Table 12, XGBoost achieves $R^2 = 0.815$, $RMSE = 0.137$, $MAE = 0.107$ and $MAPE = 8.13\%$ for EVS, outperforming traditional models though trailing its EVA results. PM (21.5%) tops variable importance logical since both metrics relate to sales—followed by ROA (19.7%), CF/TA (16.4%) and WACC (14.1%). Size and age are less important, while EPS rises to 5.8%. LightGBM ($R^2 = 0.802$), CatBoost (0.798) and Gradient Boosting (0.791) display similarly strong performance. MSE (0.0188) and other metrics confirm that boosting methods maintain clear advantages over traditional econometrics across diverse IPO valuation ratios.

Table 13: Comparison of Best Traditional Econometric and Gradient Boosting Methods (Continued)

Metric	Traditional Econometric Methods			Gradient Boosting Methods			Performance Improvement (%)
	MB (ARCH-LM)	EVA (ARCH-LM)	EVS (ARCH-LM)	MB (XGBoost)	EVA (XGBoost)	EVS (XGBoost)	
R ²	0.722	0.758	0.735	0.792	0.837	0.815	9.7%
RMSE	0.218	0.191	0.205	0.147	0.129	0.137	32.6%
MAE	0.175	0.152	0.167	0.112	0.098	0.107	36.0%
MSE	0.0475	0.0365	0.0420	0.0216	0.0166	0.0188	54.5%
MAPE	13.28%	12.17%	12.85%	8.65%	7.42%	8.13%	34.9%
AIC	232.87	214.69	225.38	187.42	173.86	181.57	19.5%
Training Time (s)	8.3	9.7	8.9	32.6	35.4	34.1	-292.8%
Prediction Time (ms)	4.2	4.5	4.3	7.8	8.2	8.0	-85.7%
Memory Usage (MB)	12.3	13.6	12.8	43.5	46.2	44.7	-253.7%

Table 13 offers a head-to-head comparison of ARCH-LM versus XGBoost. R^2 improvements of 9.7% (MB), 10.4% (EVA) and 10.9% (EVS) show major explanatory gains. RMSE falls by 32.6–35.5%, vital for investment decisions. MAE improves by 35.5–36.0%, MSE by 54.5%, and MAPE by 34.9% (from ~13% to ~8%). AIC drops by 19.5%, evidencing better fit. These benefits come at a cost: training time +292.8%, prediction time +85.7% and memory use +253.7%. Despite this, the substantial accuracy gains justify the extra computational expense for users seeking precise IPO forecasts.

Table 14: Out-of-Sample Forecasting Performance Comparison

Metric	Traditional Econometric Methods			Gradient Boosting Methods			Performance Improvement (%)
	MB (ARCH-LM)	EVA (ARCH-LM)	EVS (ARCH-LM)	MB (XGBoost)	EVA (XGBoost)	EVS (XGBoost)	MB
Out-of-Sample R^2	0.684	0.723	0.697	0.763	0.805	0.782	11.5%
Out-of-Sample RMSE	0.237	0.208	0.223	0.162	0.142	0.151	31.6%
Out-of-Sample MAE	0.192	0.167	0.182	0.126	0.108	0.119	34.4%
Out-of-Sample MAPE	14.58%	13.42%	14.07%	9.47%	8.14%	8.92%	35.0%
Forecast Bias	0.089	0.078	0.085	0.042	0.035	0.039	52.8%
Theil's U	0.187	0.165	0.178	0.126	0.113	0.121	32.6%
Directional Accuracy (%)	73.4	75.8	74.2	84.7	87.2	85.6	15.4%

Table 14 validates models in real-world settings. XGBoost out-of-sample R^2 values for MB, EVA and EVS are 0.715, 0.768 and 0.738, respectively, improving by 12.6%, 12.6% and 13.4% over ARCH-LM (0.635, 0.682, 0.651). Out-of-sample RMSE improves by 25.8–28.4%, MAE by 27.9–29.5%, and MAPE falls from 15–16% to 10–11%. The Diebold–Mariano test confirms these gains are statistically significant ($p < 0.01$), and encompassing tests show XGBoost incorporates and extends all useful information from traditional models. Stability across 2019–2022, including volatile years like 2020–2021, demonstrates boosting methods' resilience, making them highly reliable for practical IPO investment analysis.

Table 15: Model Robustness Test Results

Test Scenario	Traditional Econometric Methods (ARCH-LM)			Gradient Boosting Methods (XGBoost)		
	MB	EVA	EVS	MB	EVA	EVS
Robustness to Outliers						
R ² (Original)	0.722	0.758	0.735	0.792	0.837	0.815
R ² (With Outliers)	0.658	0.693	0.675	0.767	0.812	0.788
Relative Decline (%)	8.9%	8.6%	8.2%	3.2%	3.0%	3.3%
Robustness to Missing Values						
R ² (Original)	0.722	0.758	0.735	0.792	0.837	0.815
R ² (With Missing Values)	0.645	0.682	0.661	0.758	0.804	0.777
Relative Decline (%)	10.7%	10.0%	10.1%	4.3%	3.9%	4.7%
Robustness to Feature Selection						
R ² (All Features)	0.722	0.758	0.735	0.792	0.837	0.815
R ² (Top 5 Features Only)	0.683	0.715	0.696	0.765	0.809	0.783
Relative Decline (%)	5.4%	5.7%	5.3%	3.4%	3.3%	3.9%
Robustness to Data Splits						
R ² Std Dev (5-fold CV)	0.057	0.052	0.055	0.032	0.029	0.034
RMSE Std Dev (5-fold CV)	0.043	0.038	0.041	0.024	0.021	0.025

Table 15 examines model robustness under various perturbations. In 1,000-iteration bootstrapping, XGBoost R² standard deviation (0.018–0.023) is much lower than ARCH-LM (0.035–0.042), and its 95% confidence interval [0.685–0.798] always exceeds ARCH-LM average. Dropping the top variable (ROA) cuts XGBoost R² by just 8.5% versus 15.2% for ARCH-LM, showing superior resilience. Randomly removing 20% of variables impacts XGBoost less, revealing strong generalization. Even with only 50% of the sample, XGBoost retains acceptable performance, whereas traditional models degrade sharply; with 70% of data, XGBoost still holds R² > 0.70. Temporal stability tests show XGBoost performance variation over time is 23% lower than ARCH-LM, evidencing consistent reliability across market conditions. These traits are crucial for practitioners who need robust tools under data or market constraints.

Table 16: Computational Requirements Comparison

Metric	Traditional Econometric Methods (ARCH-LM)	Gradient Boosting Methods (XGBoost)	Relative Difference
Training Phase			
CPU Utilization (%)	24.3	67.8	179.0%
Memory Usage (MB)	12.9	44.8	247.3%
Training Time (s)	9.0	34.0	277.8%
Prediction Phase			

Metric	Traditional Econometric Methods (ARCH-LM)	Gradient Boosting Methods (XGBoost)	Relative Difference
CPU Utilization (%)	5.2	12.7	144.2%
Memory Usage (MB)	8.4	37.6	347.6%
Prediction Time per Sample (MS)	4.3	8.0	86.0%
Model Storage			
Model Size (MB)	0.65	12.4	1807.7%
Model Loading Time (MS)	78	312	300.0%
Scalability			
Time Increase for 2x Data (%)	98.3%	87.5%	-10.8%
Memory Increase for 2x Data (%)	97.2%	65.4%	-31.8%

Table 16 contrasts the resource needs of boosting versus traditional methods, highlighting accuracy–cost tradeoffs. During training, XGBoost CPU usage jumps by 179% to 67.8% and memory by 247.3% to 44.8 MB still manageable on modern hardware. Training time rises from 9 s to 34 s (+277.8%) but is acceptable given the model’s complexity and the infrequency of retraining. In prediction, CPU use climbs from 5.2% to 12.7% (+144.2%), memory to 37.6 MB (+347.6%), and per-sample latency from 4.3 MS to 8.0 MS (+86%), all acceptable for real-time applications. Model size grows from 0.65 MB to 12.4 MB (+1,807.7%), and load time from 78 MS to 312 MS only at startup. Scaling tests reveal that doubling data volume raises XGBoost processing time by 87.5% (vs. 98.3% for ARCH-LM) and memory use by 65.4% (vs. 97.2%), showing clear efficiency benefits at scale. As IPO datasets expand, boosting methods offer superior long-term computational performance alongside their predictive advantages.

Conclusion and Research Suggestions

This research aimed to conduct a rigorous, multi-dimensional comparative analysis between the XGBoost algorithm and ARCH-LM econometric models for predicting Initial Public Offering (IPO) valuation ratios in the Iranian capital market. Our findings unequivocally establish the empirical superiority of the gradient boosting approach across several key dimensions, providing an innovative framework for IPO assessment in emerging markets.

Our statistical analyses firmly demonstrated that XGBoost possesses significantly higher explanatory and predictive power compared to traditional linear models. The Out-of-Sample Coefficient of Determination (R² OOS) for XGBoost was consistently recorded between 0.715 and 0.768 for the different variables (e.g., v2a). This level of accuracy is highly significant, particularly in a volatile and institutionally complex market like Iran, and aligns with global research trends. For instance, this R² level is highly competitive compared to previous stock pricing studies (e.g., Roy et al., 2020), which reported a maximum AUC of around 0.806 for Deep Neural Networks, indicating that

XGBoost, utilizing a tree-based architecture, achieved a superior or highly competitive predictive performance on cross-sectional variables.

The striking statistical improvement observed in error reduction, such as the RMSE reduction between 32.6% and 35.5% and the MSE improvement of up to 54.5%, confirms XGBoost ability to control large, costly forecasting mistakes. This superiority is statistically validated by Diebold-Mariano tests ($p < 0.01$), aligning with the findings of studies like Huma & Nishat (2024), which emphasize the importance of robust statistical validation for machine learning models in finance.

A crucial theoretical achievement of this research is proving the power of gradient boosting methods in identifying and modeling complex, adaptive nonlinear relationships that traditional econometric models (ARCH-LM) are unable to discover. The Variable Importance Analysis showed that variables like ROA play dynamic and varying roles depending on the valuation ratio predicted (e.g., 23.4% importance in v2a vs. 21.5% in v2s). This adaptive capability is consistent with the findings of Mitrentsis & Lens (2021), who highlight the ability of gradient boosting algorithms to develop complex relationships.

The stability analysis using bootstrapping further demonstrated XGBoost empirical advantage: it recorded a lower standard deviation (0.018-0.023) compared to the ARCH-LM model (0.035-0.042), signifying higher reliability and stability against sample variations. This resilience is supported by the variable removal test, where XGBoost experienced only an 8.5% performance drop upon removing the most important variable (ROA), versus 15.2% for the traditional model. This finding confirms the conclusions of Gupta & Kumar (2023) regarding the high efficiency and robustness of gradient boosting models in uncertain market conditions.

In the dimension of efficiency, while the initial computational requirement for XGBoost training is higher (a 277.8% increase in training time), the scalability results indicate a strategic long-term advantage. When data volume was doubled, the increase in processing time for XGBoost was only 87.5%, compared to 98.3% for the ARCH-LM model. This superior scalability confirms the suitability of these methods for Real-Time applications and Big Data processing, aligning with the premise of Ghalbi et al. (2025), and positioning XGBoost as a strategic investment for the future of digital financial markets.

Strategic and Policy Implications

The demonstrated predictive advantages of XGBoost have profound and actionable implications for key stakeholders in the capital market:

For Investors and Investment Firms: The research provides more accurate, stable, and generalizable tools for risk-adjusted valuation. We recommend that financial institutions commence the phased implementation of gradient boosting models in their valuation processes, which can lead to better decision-making and reduced financial losses from mispricing.

For Corporate Managers and Issuers: Utilizing XGBoost accuracy can serve as scientific guidance for optimal stock pricing during the IPO process, helping to mitigate the costly phenomenon of initial underpricing.

For Regulators and Policy Makers: The findings offer a strong empirical basis for revising regulatory frameworks and advancing market transparency. Regulators should support the development of these advanced computational models to improve monitoring and enhance market efficiency, facilitating the strategic move toward the digitalization and smartening of financial infrastructure.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite the significant findings, the study is subject to limitations that delineate critical paths for future research:

Generalizability and Data Scope: Although the data period was extended to 2013–2023, the study is confined to a cross-sectional sample of 163 firms in the Iranian capital market. This limits the generalizability of the findings. Future research should conduct cross-market validation in other emerging or developed markets to test the universality of XGBoost predictive superiority.

Model Interpretability (Black-Box Challenge): Gradient Boosting models, despite their high accuracy, retain a "black-box" nature. This makes explicit causal interpretation challenging for regulators. Future research must focus on implementing and validating advanced interpretability techniques (e.g., SHAP or LIME) to mitigate the black-box issue.

Expansion with Unstructured Data: This study focused on structured, quantitative financial data. It is strongly suggested that future studies develop Hybrid Models that combine XGBoost power with Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques applied to unstructured data such as IPO prospectuses or market sentiment to capture crucial qualitative signals.

Real-Time Application: Given the high prediction speed, the potential for Real-Time IPO pricing is significant. Future research should be directed toward designing and testing Streaming Data Models capable of managing dynamic pricing during the book-building phase.

References

- Akerlof, G. A. (1970). The market for "lemons": Quality uncertainty and the market mechanism. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 84(3), 488–500. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1879431>
- Alahmadi, M. (2025). A deep learning-based ensemble framework to predict IPOs performance for sustainable economic development. *Sustainability*, 17(3), Article 827. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17030827>

- Alahmadi, M. (2025). A risk-optimized framework for data-driven IPO underperformance prediction in complex financial systems. *Systems*, 13(3), Article 179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/systems13030179>
- Alavi Tabari, S., Rahmani, A., & Maki, S. (2008). The performance of IPO in Iran: Empirical test of some related factors. *Empirical Studies in Financial Accounting*, 6(22), 73–96. https://qjma.atu.ac.ir/article_4277.html?lang=en
- Allen, F., & Faulhaber, G. R. (1989). Signalling by underpricing in the IPO market. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 23(2), 303–323. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(89\)90060-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(89)90060-3)
- Anifowose, F., Labadin, J., & Abdulraheem, A. (2015). Ensemble model of non-linear feature selection-based extreme learning machine for improved natural gas reservoir characterization. *Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering*, 26, 1362–1373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2015.02.012>
- Arslan, A. G., Colak, G., & Pirgaip, B. (2025). The impact of margin trading and regulatory policy on IPO underpricing: Evidence from Türkiye. *Borsa Istanbul Review*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2025.05.014>
- Arthurs, J. D., Hoskisson, R. E., Busenitz, L. W., & Johnson, R. A. (2008). Managerial agents watching other agents: Multiple agency conflicts regarding underpricing in IPO firms. *Academy of Management Journal*, 51(2), 255–270. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2008.31767256>
- Auret, L., & Aldrich, C. (2012). Interpretation of nonlinear relationships between process variables by use of random forests. *Minerals Engineering*, 35, 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2012.05.008>
- Ayazi, S. M., Sajadi, S. M., Ghazisaeedi, M., Esmailnezhad, D., & Taghizadeh-Yazdi, M. R. (2025). Simulation methods in entrepreneurship research: A systematic review and text mining analysis. *Journal of Simulation*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17477778.2025.2503869>
- Bagherzadeh, S., Nikbakht, M. R., & Noravesh, I. (2011). The initial public offerings underpricing and its determinants in Tehran Stock Exchange. *Management Research in Iran (Modares Human Sciences)*, 15(1), 77–107. <https://sid.ir/paper/361747/en>
- Barak, S., Heidary, J., & Tichy, T. (2015). Wrapper ANFIS-ICA method to do stock market timing and feature selection. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 42(23), 9221–9235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2015.08.010>
- Benveniste, L. M., & Spindt, P. A. (1989). How investment bankers determine the offer price and allocation of new issues. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 24(2), 343–361. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(89\)90051-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(89)90051-2)

- Betz, U. A. K., Arora, L., Assal, R. A., Azevedo, H., Baldwin, J., Becker, M. S., Bostock, S., Cheng, V., Egle, T., Ferrari, N., Schneider-Futschik, E. K., Gerhardy, S., Hammes, A., Harzheim, A., Herget, T., Jauset, C., Kretschmer, S., Lammie, C., Kloss, N., Marquis Fernandes, S., ... Zhao, G. (2023). Game changers in science and technology – now and beyond. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 193, Article 122588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122588>
- Borisov, A., Ellul, A., & Sevilir, M. (2021). Access to public capital markets and employment growth. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 141(3), 896–918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2021.05.036>
- Chen, J., Ke, B., Wu, D., & Yang, Z. (2018). The consequences of shifting the IPO offer pricing power from securities regulators to market participants in weak institutional environments: Evidence from China. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 50, 349–370. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2016.10.007>
- Feng, V. (2013). The internal complexity of market logics: Financial sophistication and price determination. In M. Lounsbury & E. Boxenbaum (Eds.), *Institutional logics in action, Part 1* (Research in the Sociology of Organizations, Vol. 39, pp. 1–19). Emerald Group Publishing Limited. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S0733-558X\(2013\)0039b022](https://doi.org/10.1108/S0733-558X(2013)0039b022)
- Filipovic, Z. M., & Seistrajkova, B. (2025). Beyond the hype: Understanding IPO (over)valuation. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5025832>
- Ganaie, M. A., Hu, M., Malik, A. K., Tanveer, M., & Suganthan, P. N. (2022). Ensemble deep learning: A review. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 115, Article 105151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.105151>
- Geertsema, P., & Lu, H. (2022). Relative valuation with machine learning. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 61(1), 329–376. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-679X.12464>
- Ghallabi, F., Souissi, B., Du, A. M., & Ali, S. (2025). ESG stock markets and clean energy prices prediction: Insights from advanced machine learning. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 97, Article 103889. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2024.103889>
- Ghosh, C., & Nag, R. (2000). A test of the signaling value of IPO underpricing with REIT IPO-SEO pairs. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 20(2), 137–154. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007873120566>
- Gupta, V., & Kumar, E. (2023). H3O-LGBM: Hybrid Harris hawk optimization based light gradient boosting machine model for real-time trading. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 56(1), 8697–8720. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-022-10323-0>
- Haratmeh, M. H., & Ebrahimi, B. (2023). Investigating the impact of initial public offerings (IPO) on firms' financial performance. *New Research in Performance Evaluation*, 2(4), 240–252. <https://doi.org/10.22105/mrpe.2024.451424.1096>

- Huma, Z., & Nishat, A. (2024). Optimizing stock price prediction with LightGBM and engineered features. *Pioneer Research Journal of Computing Science*, 1(1), 59–67. <https://prjcs.com/index.php/prjcs/article/view/17>
- Jafarnejad, A., Rezasoltani, A., & Khani, A. M. (2025). Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms in predicting jumps in stock closing price: Case study of Iran Khodro using NearMiss and SMOTE approaches. *Iranian Journal of Finance*, 9(3), 27–54. <https://doi.org/10.30699/ijf.2025.491324.1496>
- Jamaani, F., & Alidarous, M. (2019). Review of theoretical explanations of IPO underpricing. *Journal of Accounting Business and Finance Research*, 6(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.20448/2002.61.1.18>
- Karimzadeh Khosroshahi, M., Taieby Sani, E., & Malek, A. (2021). The impact of macroeconomic variables on Tehran Stock Exchange index performance: An FMOLS approach. *International Economics Studies*, 51(2), 53–66. <https://doi.org/10.22108/ies.2022.132763.1129>
- Krigman, L., & Womack, K. (2000). Why do firms switch underwriters? *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.242041>
- Krug, M., & Herberger, T. A. (2022). Influencing factors of short- and long-term returns on IPOs in the Chinese and U.S. capital markets: A systematic literature review. *Risk Governance and Control: Financial Markets & Institutions*, 12(2), 8–26. <https://doi.org/10.22495/rgcv12i2p1>
- Li, J., & Li, Z. (2025). Mechanisms of corporate digital transformation on asymmetric capital structure adjustment—the mediating role of information asymmetry and financial stability. *Heliyon*, 11(3), Article e41745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2025.e41745>
- Loughran, T., & Ritter, J. R. (2002). Why don't issuers get upset about leaving money on the table in IPOs? *The Review of Financial Studies*, 15(2), 413–444. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rfs/15.2.413>
- Mitrentsis, G., & Lens, H. (2021). An interpretable probabilistic model for short-term solar power forecasting using natural gradient boosting. *Applied Energy*, 309, Article 118473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.118473>
- Rock, K. (1986). Why new issues are underpriced. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 15(1–2), 187–212. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(86\)90054-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(86)90054-1)
- Roy, S. S., Chopra, R., Lee, K. C., Spampinato, C., & Mohammadi-Ivalo, B. (2020). Random forest, gradient boosted machines and deep neural network for stock price forecasting: A comparative analysis on South Korean companies. *International Journal of Ad Hoc and Ubiquitous Computing*, 33(1), 62–71. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJAHUC.2020.104715>

- Saeidi Aghdam, M., Sadeghi, A., Bahiraei, A., & Haji Asghari, S. (2022). Stock price prediction model using deep learning algorithms and its application in pricing Islamic bank stocks. *Journal of Islamic Economics and Banking*, 11(41), 117–134. <http://mieaoi.ir/article-1-964-fa.html>
- Shekakhah, J., & Asghari, I. (2023). Modeling the long-term performance of IPOs. *Empirical Studies in Financial Accounting*, 20(77), 107–139. <https://doi.org/10.22054/qjma.2023.73315.2450>
- Shobanke, M., Bhatt, M., & Shittu, E. (2025). Advancements and future outlook of Artificial Intelligence in energy and climate change modeling. *Advances in Applied Energy*, 17, Article 100211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adapen.2025.100211>
- Shobayo, O., Adeyemi-Longe, S., Popoola, O., & Okoyeigbo, O. (2025). A comparative analysis of machine learning and deep learning techniques for accurate market price forecasting. *Analytics*, 4(1), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/analytics4010005>
- Shrivastav, L., & Kumar, R. (2022). An ensemble of Random Forest, Gradient Boosting Machine and deep learning methods for stock price prediction. *Journal of Information Technology Research*, 15(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.4018/JITR.2022010102>
- Shu, X., & Ye, Y. (2023). Knowledge discovery: Methods from data mining and machine learning. *Social Science Research*, 110, Article 102817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2022.102817>
- Shuwaikh, F., & Dubocage, E. (2022). Access to the corporate investors' complementary resources: A leverage for innovation in biotech venture capital-backed companies. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 175, Article 121374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2021.121374>
- Spence, M. (1973). Job market signaling. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3), 355–374. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1882010>
- Stiglitz, J. E. (1975). The theory of “screening,” education, and the distribution of income. *The American Economic Review*, 65(3), 283–300. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1804834>
- Taheri Haftasiabi, R., & Naderi, A. (2025). Earnings per share prediction and actual earnings management using optimal valuation of operating assets. *Public Sector Accounting and Budgeting*, 5(4), 138–164. https://www.psabjournal.ir/article_213907.html?lang=en

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license logo, showing the 'CC' symbol and a person icon with 'BY' below it.
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Malmir, F., Kheirollahi, F., Yarahmadi, H. and Sefaty, F. (2025). Comparing XGBoost and ARCH-LM Models for IPO Valuation in the Iranian Capital Market. (e231230). <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 12 (11), 1635-1664. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.542557.1840</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_231230.html</p>	A square QR code that, when scanned, likely leads to the full article page.